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Pollution Reduction Potential of Bacteria Isolated from Eutrophicated Lake

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Introduction: Eutrophication is one of the most widespread environmental problems of inland waters due to the increased growth of microscopic floating plants, algae, and the formation of dense mats of larger floating plants such as water hyacinth. Water hyacinth grow only in water contaminated with point and non-point sources of pollutants. Hence, the resources get eutrophicated supporting the growth of greens. The water quality of eutrophicated lake is adversely affected and that water acts as contaminant containment.

Methods: Therefore, with the background thought that microbes degrade the pollutants, the native microorganisms isolated from the water samples of the eutrophicated lake in Lakshimpuram Lake of Theni district was mass multiplied and used for pollution degradation (1).

Results & Discussions: A total of 10 bacterial cultures were obtained. The organisms that were isolated from the eutrophicated lake was identified as *Xanthomonas*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Enterobacter*, *Pseudomonas* sp, Bacillus by comparing the morphological and bio-chemical characters with the Bergey's manual. All the cultures tend to reduce the pollution load of the eutrophicated lake. However, the best-known culture for pollution reduction was observed to be EL3 (*P. fluorescence*). EL3 recorded 75.19% reduction of total nitrogen, 88.05 % reduction of total phosphorous, and 100% reduction in heavy metals.

Conclusions: Hence, the potential of this organism may be utilized through biostimulation process to restore the eutrophicated lakes (2).

Keywords: *Water hyacinth, Bacteria, Pollution and Reduction*

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